

**PREVALENCE OF USAGE OF RESERVE ANTIBIOTICS IN MEDICAL AND
SURGICAL INTENSIVE CARE UNIT IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL AT NAVI
MUMBAI.**

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Infection with resistant organisms can result in increase in morbidity and mortality, if the initial antibiotic selection fails to offer coverage due to the association between inappropriate antibiotic selection and antibiotic resistant pattern. The selection of antibiotics is governed by antimicrobial policies in the majority of ICUs. The present study aims to evaluate the antimicrobial resistant pattern in patients admitted in Medical ICU & surgical ICU and the magnitude of usage of reserve antibiotics in MICU & SICU.

Methodology: This is a hospital record based retrospective study of six months from January 2023 to June 2023. Data on the utilization of reserve antibiotics in the MICU and SICU were collected over a six-month period. The data was analysed along with the culture and sensitivity reports of patients admitted in MICU and SICU.

Results: The higher usage of reserve antibiotics is commonly found in MICU than SICU. In MICU, the usage of Piptaz (65.66%) was higher followed by Meropenem (26.50%). And also, in SICU, usage of Piptaz (62%) was highest followed by meropenem (28%). In the total

period of study highest multidrug resistant (MDR) organisms were found in SICU (58%) than MICU (42%).

Conclusion: This data indicates that critically ill patients admitted in MICU and SICU were at very high risk of infections caused by MDR bacteria. In our study, the high usage of reserve antibiotics is noted in MICU & SICU, which needs to be controlled to avoid development of Antimicrobial Resistance.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, Intensive care unit, Multidrug Resistant, Reserve Antibiotics.

Introduction: Health care-associated infections, also known as nosocomial infections or hospital-acquired infections are by far the most frequent problems affecting hospitalized patients. There are four different types of nosocomial infections: pneumonia (ventilator-associated), surgical site infection, catheter related bloodstream infection, and catheter associated urinary tract infection. Patients in intensive care units account for 1-fourth of nosocomial infections, and over 70% of these infections are caused by organisms that are resistant to one or more antibiotics. This developing public health disaster is mainly due to the excessive use of antibiotics^[1].

When new medical procedures and alternative antimicrobials are implemented, changes in the dominant microbial aetiologies may emerge, prompting novel empiric selections. Appropriate therapy of ICU infections directed by local resistance data can have significant consequences for both the patient and the healthcare system^[2]. An increase in age, illness, severity, and debility, a lengthy stay in the intensive care unit, the use of previous antibiotics, and contact with indwelling prosthetic devices are all associated with an increased risk of developing an infection with antibiotic-resistant organisms. Infection with resistant organisms can result in a bad outcome if the initial antibiotic selection fails to offer coverage due to the association between inappropriate antibiotic selection and antibiotic resistant pattern. The selection of antibiotics is governed by antimicrobial policies in the majority of ICUs.^[3]

Material and methods: Place of study- Department of microbiology, Medical intensive care unit and surgical intensive care unit of MGM hospital, Kamothe, Navi Mumbai.

Period of study- 6 months (January 2023 – June 2023)

Type of study – Retrospective study

Procedure – It is a hospital record based retrospective study conducted in Medical Intensive Unit (MICU) and Surgical Intensive Unit (SICU) of MGM Medical College and

Hospital, Kamothe, Navi Mumbai. Data regarding usage of reserve antibiotics in MICU and SICU during the 6 months period from January 2023 to June 2023 was collected.

The records of the pathogenic organisms found in various microbiological samples—such as blood, urine, and wounds—that were sent from intensive care unit patients to the microbiology laboratory for regular diagnosis were obtained and examined from the Hospital Information Management System (HIMS).

Microbiological specimens processing and identification of isolated organisms- Sample processing and identification of the microorganism were performed as per the standard operating procedures of our laboratory. Following the standards of the Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines, the antimicrobial susceptibilities of the bacterial isolates were determined using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method.

The antimicrobial susceptibility assay was performed on Mueller Hinton agar by the disc diffusion method and growth inhibition zones were interpreted according to the Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines.

Data Analysis- The data was analyzed along with the culture and sensitivity reports of patients admitted in MICU and SICU.

During rounds, the clinicians were advised regarding change in the antibiotic use when required as per culture and sensitivity reports.

Ethics- Ethical approval for this study was taken from the Institutional Ethical Committee of MGM Medical College.

Results: Over a period of study, table no 1 and graph no 1 shows the total growth percentage of gram-positive cocci and gram-negative bacilli organisms isolated in SICU and MICU.

Table No 1

Organism	GPC	GNB
SICU	13.70%	27.45 %
MICU	86.20%	72.54 %

Graph No 1

Above data shows total growth rate of gram positive and gram-negative organisms in SICU and MICU

Table no 2 and Graph no 2 Usage rates of reserve antibiotics in MICU and SICU

Table no 2

Name of Reserve Antibiotics	MICU	SICU
PIPTAZ	65.66%	62%
MEROPENEM	26.50%	28%
POLYMYXIN B	3.61%	10%
VANCOMYCIN	3.61%	0%
COLISTIN	0.60%	0%

Graph no 2

The utilization of reserve antibiotics was observed to be higher in the MICU compared to the SICU. In the MICU, Piptaz was the most frequently administered antibiotic, accounting for 65.66% of usage, followed by Meropenem at 26.50%. Similarly, in the SICU, Piperacillin-Tazobactam was also the most commonly used (62%), with Meropenem being the second most utilized antibiotic (28%).

Graph no 3 The rate of multidrug resistant organisms in MICU and SICU monthly and overall

Graph no 3

In the total period of study highest multidrug resistant (MDR) organisms were found in SICU (58%) than MICU (42%).

Graph no 4 shows the growth rate of each gram-positive organisms in SICU and MICU

Graph No 4

Above table and graph shows that the growth rate of gram-positive organism in which the higher growth of CONS (56 %) is seen in MICU followed by enterococcus (20%), streptococcus (16%) and staphylococcus (8%) while in SICU, enterococcus (50%) was seen in highest rate followed by streptococcus (25%) and staphylococcus (25%).

Graph no 5 shows the growth rate of each gram-negative organisms in SICU and MICU

The graph shows the percentage distribution of Gram-negative bacterial isolates from clinical samples in the Surgical ICU (SICU) and Medical ICU (MICU). Each bar indicates the proportion of a specific pathogen in each unit.

Discussion: This study was carried out in MICU and SICU of MGM Hospital, Kamothe, Navi Mumbai. The study duration was 6 months; data was collected and analyzed according to culture and sensitivity report.

Table No 1 and graph no 1 showed the growth of gram-positive organism was higher (86.20%) than gram negative organism (72.54%) in MICU. Also, in SICU growth of gram-positive organism was less (13.70%) than gram negative organism (27.45%). Similarly, comparable results were found by Halim *et al* where gram-negative bacteria took the upper hand among all nosocomial pathogens (53%) while gram-positive organisms represented 37.9%.^[7]

Table no 2 and graph no 2 showed in MICU highest use of reserve antibiotics were Piptaz(65.66%) meropenem(26.50%) Polymyxin B (3.61%), vancomycin (3.61%) lastly colistin (0.60%)and in SICU Piptaz (62%) was highest followed by meropenem (28%) and polymyxin B (10%). Similar study conducted by Vu Quoc Dat *et al*, showed highest use of antibiotics were the third generation cephalosporins, fluoroquinolones, and carbapenems in the CCUs setting. The high frequency of Watch and Reserve group antibiotics (87.3% and 0.54% respectively^[4]. Also Results of Shebl and Mosaad *et al* from Egypt were in contrast to the current study as regards vancomycin and linezolid with a resistance of 10.8% and 11.3%, respectively ^[5]

Another study conducted by Williams A *et al* the five most utilized antimicrobial agents were third-generation cephalosporins (18.48 %), meropenem (16.47%), levofloxacin (15.97%), metronidazole (14.65%), and ceftriaxone (13.42%)^[6]

According to graph No. 3, the overall percentage of MDR organisms in the MICU was 42%, whereas in the SICU it was 58%. Multidrug resistance is highly prevalent, particularly among gram-negative organisms, as shown by the study by NohaAlaaEldin Fahim *et al*. The most multidrug-resistant bacteria were Klebsiella (87.84%) and Acinetobacter (83.59%)^[7].

The graph 4 presents the distribution of Gram-positive bacterial isolates in SICU and MICU settings. Enterococcus spp. was the most commonly isolated organism in SICU (59%), compared to 20% in MICU. Staphylococcus spp. and Streptococcus spp. were observed at lower but equal frequencies in SICU (2.5% each), with slightly lower rates in MICU. Interestingly, Coagulase-Negative Staphylococci (CONS) were detected exclusively in MICU (56%), possibly reflecting increased use of invasive devices such as central lines and catheters, which are well-known risk factors for CONS-related bloodstream infections ^[8].

These findings are consistent with previous studies indicating that Enterococcus spp. tend to dominate in surgical patients due to prolonged hospital stay, antibiotic exposure, and gastrointestinal procedures ^[9]. The higher prevalence of CONS in MICU aligns with reports from tertiary care hospitals in India and abroad, where CONS are recognized as leading causes of catheter-related infections in critically ill patients ^[10,11]. This distribution underlines the importance of strict aseptic protocols and targeted antibiotic therapy to mitigate Gram-positive infections in ICU environments.

The graph 5 illustrates the distribution of Gram-negative bacterial isolates in the SICU and MICU. *Acinetobacter* spp. and *E. coli* were the most commonly isolated organisms in both units, with slightly higher prevalence in SICU (28.57% each) compared to MICU. *Klebsiella* spp. showed higher occurrence in MICU (22.97%) than SICU (7.14%), while *Citrobacter* and *Enterobacter* species were more frequently detected in SICU. The presence of *Pseudomonas* and *Proteus* was comparatively low in both settings.

These findings are consistent with studies conducted in Indian tertiary care hospitals, where *Acinetobacter baumannii* and *E. coli* have been reported as dominant pathogens in ICU-acquired infections due to their high resistance profiles and association with ventilator-associated pneumonia and bloodstream infections ^[12,13]. A study by Mehta et al. reported *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Acinetobacter* spp. as leading Gram-negative isolates in ICU bloodstream infections, aligning with the present data ^[10]. Additionally, the ICMR-AMRSN 2023 report highlights *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* as major contributors to antimicrobial resistance in critical care units, reinforcing the need for targeted infection control and stewardship practices ^[11].

Conclusion:

- This study suggests that excessive use of reserve antibiotics in MICU and SICU leads to development of resistance to multiple antibiotics that could pose a challenging issue in the therapeutic outcome of patients
- Also, this data indicates that critically ill patients admitted in MICU and SICU were at very high risk of infections caused by MDR bacteria.
- In our study, the high usage of reserve antibiotics is noted in MICU & SICU, which needs to be controlled to avoid development of Antimicrobial Resistance.
- More studies need to be conducted to obtain a complete picture of the local and international situation of AMR.
- Control of Antibiotic resistance is mandatory to see the effective antibiotic stewardship before reaching a deadlock.

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